

Simple Tax Analysis of Hunter BHR Equity Arrangement

Resource: AP

Background

Skancateles LLC(SKA) subscribed to RMB3m in return for 10% of equity interest in Bohai Harvest RST (Shanghai) Equity Investment Fund Management Co., Ltd (BHR), a company established in the People's Republic of China (PRC) with a registered capital of RMB30m on December 16, 2013.¹

Tax citizen status

BHR is a firm incorporated in PRC which adopted limited liability corporation form and is a PRC tax resident, both domestic and overseas income of which should be reported to Chinese Communist Party (CCP) tax authority and taxed in PRC.² SKA is an American company that is a non-resident taxpayer with only income from PRC subject to PRC regulation, and is a resident taxpayer of the USA with global income subject to IRS regulation. SKA should report its overseas assets to IRS pursuant to Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act (FATCA) requirement.³

Possible ways of tax avoidance and economic realisation

¹ Loan agreement <https://gnews.org/444046/>

² *Enterprises Income Tax*

Law.http://www.fdi.gov.cn/1800000121_39_3339_0_7.html#:~:text=Article%20%20Enterprises%20are%20classified%20into%20resident%20and%20non%2Dresident%20enterprises.&text=Article%204%20The%20enterprise%20income,tax%20rate%20shall%20be%2020%25

³ IRS requirement <https://www.irs.gov/businesses/corporations/fatca-information-for-individuals>

*PRC Companies Law*⁴ provided the exception of dividend payment non-prorated to shareholding ratio pursuant to provisions in the constitutions of companies provided determined by all the shareholders. Therefore, it couldn't be assumed that only 10% of profit realised by BHR would be distributed to SKA. However, if dividend was distributed, there would be taxable income that should be reported to IRS, which may be exposed to American media and other US authorities.

Whoever made business in PRC knows that expense reimbursement, related transactions at transfer price and other methods, such as paying expenses of parties to loans mentioned above, compensation to Crystal Liu or transfer to tax heavens, rather than dividend distribution would usually be considered for economic interest realisation. Although both the *Tax Collection Administration Law*⁵ and *Enterprises Income Tax Law* of PRC provided that transactions between related parties, including consideration payment and revenue collection charged not at prices that were charged between independent parties, were subject to tax authorities' adjustment power. Therefore, it can be inferred that there were two tax avoidance ways.

1. Covering up related parties (Prices assumed to be charged independently are not subject to adjustment);
2. Despite obviously being related parties, no investigation and no adjustment by tax authorities (Lack of rule of law in PRC, inspection of CCP tax authorities must be signed off by chief of tax authorities not lower than county).

PRC had commenced governmental negotiation of FATCA since 2012 and concluded on the substantial content with USA in June 2014. Financial institutions in PRC should report information of American tax residents to IRS. Otherwise, such nations' income arising from the USA should be charged withholding tax of 30%. Transactions that transfer economic interest to tax heavens conducted by BHR circulating American financial accounts in PRC don't have to be filed for IRS by financial institutions in PRC.

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⁴ PRC Companies Law
http://www.fdi.gov.cn/1800000121_39_4814_0_7.html#:~:text=Article%201%3A%20The%20Company%20Law,and%20economic%20order%20and%20promote

⁵ *Tax Collection Administration Law* http://english1.english.gov.cn/laws/2005-09/12/content_31187.htm